

PERCEPTION OF THEATRE PERSONNEL TOWARD THE USE OF ALDERETE SCALE IN POST ANAESTHESIA CARE UNIT MANAGEMENT OF PATIENTS IN USMANU DAN FODIYO UNIVERSITY TEACHING HOSPITAL, SOKOTO

Akhimie Oyakilome¹ RN MSc, Abdullahi Umar² RN BSc, Kombo Abdulrahman Salihu³ RN Phd, Auwal Mohammad⁴ RN Phd,

^{1,2,4}Usmanu Danfodiyo University Teaching Hospital Sokoto

³Ahmadu Bello University Zaria

Correspondence: Akhimie Oyakilome¹ RN MSc kourhage@gmail.com

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.16969777>

Article Received 12-05-2025 / Article Accepted 23-07-2025 / Article Published 30-07-2025

ABSTRACT:

Nurses play significant role in the care and management of patients at different stages of the surgical process. The surgical process includes preoperative preparation, intra-operative care or interventions and post-operative management and care interventions for the patient's recovery after surgery. Intraoperative care is a process that begins when the patient has being taken to the operating room and continues until they leave the operating room. The study aimed at evaluating the perception of theatre personnel towards the use of modified alderete scale in post anaesthesia care unit management of patient of Usmanu Danfodiyo University Teaching Hospital, Sokoto. The study employed a descriptive cross-sectional design. A stratified random sampling technique was used to select 43 theatre personnel. Descriptive statistics like frequency, mean, standard deviation and percentage were used to describe the distribution of data. Pearson's rank correlation was used in determining the relationship between knowledge and level of utilization of pain scales in pain management at the $p=0.05$ level of significance. A total of 43 study participants were involved in this study. More than half of the personnel 28 (65.15%), were males; 18 (41.9%) of them were in the age category of 34-39 years with mean age of 36.74 and standard deviation of ± 2.917 . The magnitude of good knowledge towards modified alderete scale in PACU management of patients among theatre personnel was

This work is licensed under a [Creative Commons Attribution 4.0 International License](https://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0/).

How to Cite

Akhimie Oyakilome RN MSc, Abdullahi Umar RN BSc, Kombo Abdulrahman Salihu RN Phd, Auwal Mohammad RN Phd., (2025). PERCEPTION OF THEATRE PERSONNEL TOWARD THE USE OF ALDERETE SCALE IN POST ANAESTHESIA CARE UNIT MANAGEMENT OF PATIENTS IN USMANU DAN FODIYO UNIVERSITY TEACHING HOSPITAL, SOKOTO. *International Journal of Medical Sciences and Academic Research*, 6(04). <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.16969777>

81.4% with a mean score of 9.17 ± 0.161 . The magnitude of good attitude towards using modified alderete scale among theatre personnel was 95.3% with a mean score of 25.17 ± 2.290 . The magnitude for the level of utilization of pain assessment scale in pain management was 18.6%. The study revealed that theatre personnel working in post anaesthesia care unit of Usman Danfodiyo University Teaching Hospital, Sokoto had good knowledge, good attitude towards the use of modified alderete scale managing patients.

Keywords: Alderete, Perception, Personnel

INTRODUCTION:

There have been giant strides in technological and scientific developments in surgical treatment and postoperative care minimize the risk of surgical treatments, improve the treatment and care of patients, and increase the quality of life (Selda Mert, 2023). Globally an estimated 234 million surgeries are performed annually, making surgical care an essential part of healthcare (Gürel and Koçaşlı, 2022). Nurses play significant role in the care and management of patients at different stages of the surgical process. The surgical process includes preoperative preparation, intra-operative care or interventions and post-operative management and care interventions for the patient's recovery after surgery. Intraoperative care is a process that begins when the patient has being taken to the operating room and continues until they leave the operating room (Gürel and Koçaşlı, 2022).

The postoperative period commences from post-anaesthesia care unit (PACU). The most frequent disturbances during the immediate postoperative period in PACU are acute pain, nausea and vomiting, delirium, shivering, dry mouth, and hunger (Santry, Strassels, Ingraham, et al 2020). Postoperative care in early recovery should involve airway management and oxygen therapy, vital signs monitoring, postoperative pain management, postoperative nausea and vomiting treatment, treating post anesthesia shivering, and monitoring surgical sites for complications such as bleeding, discharge, swelling, hematoma, wound healing, and infection (Santry, Strassels, Ingraham, et al 2020)

Nursing care is significant in PACU to improve the quality of recovery of patients and to prevent complications that may occur. Nurses must be highly qualified and have knowledge and skills in the treatment and care of patients from different surgeries of varying complexity that require specialized and individualized care (Selda Mert, 2023). Nursing care in the recovery room is focused on the patient's condition after surgical intervention with its main purpose of providing direct and continuous patient observation in emergence from general or regional anesthesia. In the absence of professional assistance, patients can develop complications that can lead them into shock or death (Niyungeko, Gasaba, Ndayisaba, Ndikumana, Ndayisaba, Uwamahoro, Nzobakenga et al, 2021).

The use of Alderete's score chart has provided use of a standardized tool that provides consistency in monitoring thus reducing errors that may occur after anesthesia. In countries where the tool has been in use, it has been effective in detection of any deviation from the normal parameters leading to effective and prompt thus preventing post anesthesia complications and subsequent deaths Odundo, Omondi and Omuga (2020). Alderete's scoring system includes assessing a patient's responsiveness, activity or movement of limbs, respiration, blood pressure and oxygen saturation level as determined by pulse oximetry. A score of 0 to 2 is given for each of the five categories assessed and a score of 8 to 10 is considered adequate for discharge of the patient from the post anesthesia care unit to the post-surgical ward. A patient with a score of less than 8 is considered not ready for discharge and has to be monitored until a desired score is achieved

MATERIAL&METHOD:

A descriptive cross-sectional design was used to determine the level of knowledge, perceived attitude and reported utilization of alderete's scale in post anaesthesia care unit management of patients among theatre personnel's of UDUTH. UDUTH Sokoto is a tertiary health institution serving as a referral centre to all primary and secondary health facilities in its catchment area which consist of Sokoto, Kebbi, Zamfara, Katsina and Niger states. It commenced operation in 1989 and is a 650 bed hospital with various specialties. The population for the study is a total of 43 nurses who work in the main operating theatre the hospital. Using existing strata, a stratified random sampling technique was used to select 43 nurses.

The instrument for data collection is a questionnaire designed by the researcher covering objective 1, 2

and 3. The questionnaire comprised of 37 items in English, including 6 demographic questions, 11 knowledge questions, and the interviewees were asked to reply in two ways: 1 = Yes; 0 = No, with a total range of "0-10"; they were asked to answer 7 attitude questions according to five-point Likert scales: from "strongly agree = 5" to "strongly disagree = 1"; they were asked to answer 6 practice questions according to five-point Likert scales: from "always = 5" to "less often = 1" with a total score range of "6-30"; and they were asked to choose from 8 barriers questions that applies to them. Answers were evaluated considering the extent to which they are compatible with pain therapy standards commonly acknowledged by the international pain management guidelines. A knowledge score of 0-5 means poor knowledge and 6-11 means good knowledge.

Section A	Elicited information on the respondents' demographic profile in terms of; age, gender, ethnic group, religion, marital status, rank and years of service.
Section B	Focused on the knowledge of alderete's scale in post anaesthesia care unit management of patients among theatre personnel'
Section C	Attitude of personnel in the use of alderete's scale in post anaesthesia care unit management of patients
Section D	Practicability of the use of alderete's scale in post anaesthesia care unit management of patients among theatre personnel'
Section E	Factors affecting the use of alderete's scale in post anaesthesia care unit management of patients among theatre personnel'

Data collection and analysis

The questionnaire was designed using google form and link shared with the theatre personnel using their contact numbers and this lasted for two weeks. Therefore two weeks was used for data collection. Data obtained through the questionnaire was appropriately cleaned to ensure accuracy and consistency. The data collected was analyzed using the Statistical package for social science version 23. The respondents' demographics, alderete's assessment tool-related knowledge, attitude, and

practice were analyzed using frequencies and percentages

Ethical consideration

All information about the study was explained to the participants for them to understand the purpose of the study which is academic and therefore informed Participants are informed that participation is voluntary and they can withdraw at anytime

RESULT:

A total of 51 self-administered questionnaires was sent electronically to the respondents out of which

43 (84.3%) responded and were completely filled and 4 did not respond and 4 incompletely filled. The analysis was based on the 43 completely filled questionnaires retrieved.

Table 1: Socio-demographic characteristics of respondents N=43

Variable	Categories	Frequency	Percentage (%)	Mean±SD
Gender	Male	28	65.1	
	Female	15	34.9	
Age	22-27	5	11.6	
	28-33	9	20.9	
	34-39	18	41.9	36.74±2.917
	40-45	5	11.6	
	46+	6	14.0	
Educational Attainment	Registered Perioperative Nurse	29	67.4	
	Registered Anaesthetist Nurse	9	20.1	
	BNSc	5	11.5	
Position/Rank	Nursing Officer	7	16.3	
	Senior Nursing Officer	15	34.9	
	Principal Nursing Officer	4	9.3	
	Assistant Chief Nursing Officer	3	6.9	
	Chief Nursing Officer	9	20.9	
	Others	5	11.7	
Duration in position	Less than 3	31	72.1	
	4-6 years	7	16.3	
	7-9 years	3	6.9	
	10 years and above	2	4.7	
Number of years Registered Nurse	0-5 years	7	16.3	
	6-10 years	10	23.3	
	11-15 years	15	34.9	
	16-20 years	4	9.3	
	21 years and above	7	16.3	

Source: Field data 2024

Table 1 displays socio – demographic characteristics of nurses who participated in the study. The Study covered age group, gender, educational attainment, Position/rank, duration in the position (in years), number of years as registered nurse Majority of the nurses are within the age brackets of 34 – 39 representing 41.9%. Male nurses are almost double of female nurses representing 65.1%. Most of the respondents are registered perioperative nurses representing 67.4%

while 11.5% hold Bachelor's degree in Nursing. Most of the respondents are Senior Nursing Officers representing 34.9%, and other ranks (assistant director and deputy director) represented 11.7% of the respondents. The duration in the position (years) by nurses was mostly majority of nurses was less than 3 years representing 72.1% and those with 10 years and above representing 4.7%. 34.9% of the respondents have 11-15 years' experience while those with 21 years and above are 16.3%.

Table 2: Level of Nurses' Knowledge about alderate tool/scale Patient Management (N=43)

Knowledge status	N	Percentage	Mean ± SD
Good Knowledge	35	81.4%	9.17 ± 0.161
Poor Knowledge	8	18.6%	6.50 ± 0.189
Total	43	100	

Source: Field data 2024

From the table 2 above it shows that 81.4% of the respondents have good knowledge about the modified alderate tool while 16.8% of them have poor knowledge about modified alderate tool/scale.

Table 3: Attitude of Theatre Personnel on the Use of Modified Alderate Scale in patient management

Attitude	N	Percentage	Mean ± SD
Positive Attitude	41	95.3	25.17 ± 2.290
Negative Attitude	2	4.7	19.00 ± 0.00
Total	43	100	

Source: Field data 2024

From the table 3 above it shows that 95.3% of the respondents have good attitude about the modified alderate tool while 4.7% of them have negative attitude knowledge about modified alderate tool/scale.

Table 4: Use of Modified Alderate Scale in patient management in PACU

Item	Less Often	Sometimes	Never	Often	Frequently
Prior to admitting patient, I ensure all monitors are functioning	0	1 (2.33)	0	14 (32.56)	28 (65.12)
I use Modified Alderete scale in monitoring all patients in PACU	12 (27.91)	23 (53.49)	0	6 (13.95)	2 (4.65)
I usually communicate findings (during handing over) or discharging patients	2 (4.65)	6 (13.95)	2 (4.65)	15 (34.88)	18 (41.86)
I ensure proper documentation of findings after assessing the patient	1 (2.33)	6 (13.95)	2 (4.65)	12 (27.91)	22 (51.16)
Modified alderete chart always tell the true state about the patient	0	2 (4.65)	0	11 (25.58)	30 (69.77)
Patients to be discharged must have a score greater than 8	0	6 (13.95)	2 (4.65)	12 (27.91)	23 (53.49)

The table above depicts that participants indicate the leading frequency of items on usage of modified alderete assessment scale in the management of patients that “Modified alderete chart always tell the true state about the patient” with 69.77%, “Prior

to admitting patient I ensure all monitors are functioning” with 65.12% and “Patients to be discharged must have a score greater than 8” with 53.49%. Those who use Modified Alderete scale in monitoring all patients in PACU both often and frequently are 13.95% and 4.65% totally 18.6%

Table 5: Factors Affecting the Use of Modified Alderate Scale in patient management

S/N	Factor	True (%)	False (%)
1	Shortage of nurses hinders the use of Alderete's chart in the hospital	36 (83.7)	7 (16.3)
2	Monitoring patients using Alderete's chart is cumbersome	24 (55.8)	19 (44.2)
3	Unavailability of modified Alderete scale in patient management	28 (65.1)	15 (34.9)
4	High patients to Personnels ratio in Post Anaesthesia Care Unit making the use of scoring system impossible	32 (74.4)	11 (25.6)
5	Poor documentation as a result of non-availability of charts	37 (86.0)	6 (14.0)
6	Lack of familiarity with assessment tools	30 (69.8)	13 (30.2)
7	Lack of knowledge about modified Alderete chart	29 (67.4)	14 (32.6)
8	Unconducive working environment	27 (62.8)	16 (37.2)

Source: Field data, 2024

Table 5 shows factors affecting the use of modified alderate tool/scale. The theatre personnel reveal that three leading factors affecting the use of modified alderate scale: "Poor documentation as a result of

Table 6: Relationship between knowledge and Utilization alderate scale in patient management (N=43)

Knowledge versus Utilization	Mean \pm SD	r-value	P-value
Knowledge	13.79 \pm 1.440	0.199	0.222
Practice	25.09 \pm 4.070		

Table 6 shows that at 0.05 level of significance, there was no significant relationship between knowledge and reported practice of the use of modified alderate assessment scale in PACU management of patients in UDUTH with $r=0.199$, $p<0.05$. Now, this suggests that knowledge and usage of modified alderate scale are independent and not related with each other.

DISCUSSION:

Findings in the study shows 81.4% of theatre personnel had good knowledge about the modified alderate tool. This finding was consistent with a study conducted by Odundo, Omondi and Omuga (2020), which revealed that 93% of staff had knowledge about Alderete tool. Staffs that have the required knowledge and skills will be better placed to use the Alderete's score chart more effectively.

The study also showed that 4.7% of the respondents have negative attitude about the modified alderate tool. This is far less than that conducted in Kenya which revealed that 29% of nurses had negative attitude towards the use of Alderete's chart in monitoring patients. The reason to the aforementioned as reported in 55.8% of theatre personnel was that the chart been cumbersome and time wasting which is also similar to that conducted in Kenya with 66% of nurses reported the use of Alderete's score chart in monitoring Post anaesthesia

non-availability of charts" representing 86%, "Shortage of nurses hinders the use of Alderete's chart in the hospital" representing 83.7% and "High patients to Personnel's ratio in Post Anaesthesia Care Unit making the use of scoring system impossible" representing 74.4%.

patients that is was cumbersome (Odundo, Omondi and Omuga, 2020).

The study also revealed that three leading factors affecting the use of modified alderate scale: "Poor documentation as a result of non-availability of charts" representing 86%, "Shortage of nurses hinders the use of Alderete's chart in the hospital" representing 83.7% and "High patients to Personnel's ratio in Post Anaesthesia Care Unit making the use of scoring system impossible" representing 74.4% affected the use of alderete tool in patients management which is similar to a study conducted by (Street, Phillips, Kent, Colgan and Mohebbi, 2015) which revealed that Staff factors that have affected utilization of the monitoring tool include knowledge, skills and attitude towards the use of the chart. Institutional factors have also affected the utilization of monitoring tool and these are policies governing the use of the tool and supply of resources necessary for the utilization of the scoring tool. This is also similar to the study conducted by (Buerhaus, Donelan, Ulrich, Norman, DesRoches and Dittus, 2007) in which it was observed that shortage of nurses affected the delivery of health care.

The study revealed that at 0.05 level of significance, there was no significant relationship between knowledge and reported practice of the use of modified alderate assessment scale in PACU management of patients in UDUTH with $r=0.199$,

$p < 0.05$. Now, this suggests that knowledge and usage of modified alderate scale are independent and not related with each other

Limitation

Firstly, the study was carried out in UDUTH it is pertinent to note that the results cannot be generalized for the entire nurses in the state. However, the study can be extended to cover the entire state in Northern Nigeria. Secondly, the study assessed reported utilization of alderetescales in post anaesthesia care unit management of patients among theatre personnel. Observation on the use of alderetescales among theatre personnel would have been more appropriate. Finally, factors identified to have impinged on the use of alderete scale in post anaesthesia care unit management of patients are skewed negatively as it was only on the staff without noting what the management has to say.

CONCLUSION:

On the basis of the findings of this study, the following conclusions were drawn:

It was seen that theatre personnel had good knowledge about alderete scale in post anaesthesia care unit management of patient and their knowledge is consistent with nurses in other parts of the world. Furthermore, the study revealed that patient's workload and lack of assessment protocols were the two leading factors militating against the use of alderetescale in post anaesthesia care unit management of patient. Also, there was no significant relationship between knowledge and reported practice of the use of modified alderete assessment scale in PACU management of patients of UDUTH, Sokoto

Conflict of interest:

There is no conflict of interest in this paper.

REFERENCE:

1. Buerhaus PI, Donelan K, Ulrich BT, Norman L, DesRoches C, Dittus R. Impact of the nurse shortage on hospital patient care: Comparative perspectives. *Heal Affa.* 2007;26(3):853-62.
2. Gürel, B., & Koçuşlı, S. (2022). Compilation quality and nursing care of patients after surgery. *Turkey Health Sciences and Research Journal*, 5(1), 12-30. <https://doi.org/10.51536/tusbad.1035512>
3. Niyungeko, Darius & Gasaba, Emmanuel & Ndayisaba, Ariane & Ndikumana, Jean & Ndayisaba, Justin & Uwamahoro, Amina & Nzobakenga, Angèle & Nishimwe, Esdras & Ndikumana, Margueritte & Barbara, Rose. (2021). Nursing Practice in Recovery Room: A Case of Kibuye Hope Hospital and Mutoyi Hospital. *Open Journal of Nursing*. 11. 139-151. [10.4236/ojn.2021.113013](https://doi.org/10.4236/ojn.2021.113013).
4. Odundo RA, Omondi L, Omuga B. (2020) Utilization of Alderete's Score Chart in Monitoring Post Anesthesia Patients: Are Nurses Utilizing the Monitoring Tool?. *Int J Rec Innov Med Clin Res*;2(4):49-55.
5. Santry, H.P., Strassels, S.A., Ingraham, A.M. et al (2020). Identifying the fundamental structures and processes of care contributing to emergency general surgery quality using a mixed-methods Donabedian approach. *BMC Med Res Methodol* 20, 247. <https://doi.org/10.1186/s12874-020-01096-7>
6. Selda M,. (2023). The Significance of Nursing Care in the Post-anesthesia Care Unit and Barriers to Care. *Intensive Care Research*. 3. [10.1007/s44231-023-00052-5](https://doi.org/10.1007/s44231-023-00052-5)
7. Street M, Phillips NM, Kent B, Colgan S, Mohebbi M. Minimising post-operative risk using a Post-Anaesthetic Care Tool (PACT): protocol for a prospective observational study and cost effectiveness analysis. *BMJ Open*. 2015;5(6):e007